

Turing Way – Athena Prize Nomination

Submission prepared by Malvika Sharan (The Turing Way project Co-lead, Senior Researcher - The Alan Turing Institute), Arielle Bennett (Programme Manager - Tools. Practices and Systems, The Alan Turing Institute), Amy Gallimore (EDI Strategy Officer-Tools. Practices and Systems, The Alan Turing Institute), Kirstie Whitaker (Programme Director - Tools. Practices and Systems, The Alan Turing Institute)

<https://royalsociety.org/grants-schemes-awards/awards/athena-prize/>

Section 2 – Nomination details – nominator This section is for the nominator to complete Please provide a statement of support outlining the suitability of the team for this prize (500 words maximum). Please be sure to clearly include the name of the programme or initiative and the names of the individuals making up the nominated team.

My nomination is for *The Turing Way* project led by Dr. Kirstie Whitaker and Dr. Malvika Sharan, representing a [core team](#) of 14 members and a community of more than 300 contributors from around the world. *The Turing Way* champions diversity by challenging traditionally siloed research cultures from every angle and provides a community driven handbook for conducting research in a way that welcomes and supports a truly diverse group of researchers. *The Turing Way* has embedded equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) at the very core of its work and has made significant contributions to the wider STEM field on several levels.

The Turing Way is much more than a book: it is a 'community of practice' that promotes a culture of collaboration among global contributors with a diverse range of domain expertise. As a community-developed resource, the project belongs to the community and is always a work in progress. Shared under an open licence, everyone can freely read, reuse, distribute, modify, and contribute back to the resources. The project itself is built upon open source infrastructures such as Git, Jupyter Book and Netlify.

The content of the project focuses on topics that are fundamentally linked to EDI principles. As well as being a guide to reproducible research and scientific communication, the Turing way focuses on collaboration and ethical research. The Guide for Collaboration provides recommendations for researchers on how to build diverse teams and create inclusive workspaces spanning topics from remote working to running inclusive events and participatory co-creation. The Guide to Research Ethics grapples with the realities of ethical research, shares key principles from Responsible Research and Innovation and Research Integrity, as well as sections on activism and internal policy advocacy.

Significantly, *The Turing Way* team hasn't produced these guides by choosing a select group of people to decide what is "best practice" but has provided a working example of team science, using a wide community to define the standards and expectations the community would like to see in responsible and ethical research practice. This approach has empowered diverse individuals from different backgrounds, identities and lived experiences

to express their viewpoints, fairly represent different realities in research and particularly involve voices from communities that are traditionally marginalised in STEM.

Recent reports have highlighted how much must change in UK research culture for the ambitions we all share in terms of diversity to be realised. *The Turing Way* is different to other projects focused on diversifying data science in that it has fully embraced the need to change scientific and research culture for the better, in order to support inclusive research for diverse researchers. *The Turing Way* provides a blueprint for what needs to change, but also evidence of how to co-create meaningful practices through collaboration.

Ultimately the project has enabled thousands of contributors to share their vision of what a truly global research culture would look like and have presented that knowledge in an entirely accessible and open format.

Section 3 – Nomination details – nominated team

This section is for a representative of the nominated team to complete

3.1) Please provide a summary of your initiative or project (500 words maximum). This should include:

- *The aims of the initiative or project (what you hoped to achieve at the end)*
- *How you achieved your aim*
- *Your team's role in the activity*
- *Timescales*
- *How you measured success*
- *Any support or funding received*

The Turing Way is an open source and community-led project that aims to open up the potential of data science for everyone. Our project brings together a diverse community of researchers, educators, learners, administrators, and stakeholders from within The Alan Turing Institute, across the UK, and internationally. We have collectively written a web-based book with five guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration and Ethical Research, as well as a Community Handbook. We seek to provide all the information that researchers need at the start of their projects to ensure that they are conducting research that is ethical, inclusive and easy to reproduce at the end.

The project started in 2018, funded initially by the AI for Science and Government Strategic Priority Fund, and is led by Kirstie Whitaker, Programme Director of the Tools, Practices and Systems Programme (TPS) at The Alan Turing Institute and Malvika Sharan, TPS Senior Researcher and lead of the Community Management Team at the Turing.

To foster a welcoming and supportive community, *The Turing Way* embraced online working from the start. Since the book's launch in 2019, the team has hosted regular events, including training workshops, remote co-working sessions, speaking engagements, mentored contribution sprints and project-specific consulting. An example of best practice in inclusive remote working is our [Book Dash event](#), where participants collaborate on *The Turing Way* book synchronously. Book Dashes moved online in 2020 to ensure that international participants had an equal chance to participate, with sessions planned to enable flexible participation from different time zones. We pay for accessibility requirements for the participants, including access to high-speed internet, childcare grants, live transcription services, and subsistence costs. The event design and support have enabled participants from African, Asian, European, Latin and North American countries to contribute.

We measure the project's success through the diversity of contributions to the project and the impact seen on the wider STEM sector. Within a year of starting, the project expanded from a single guide, to the current five, all written in the open on GitHub by our 300+ community members. The 200 subchapters cover topics including open science, data management, research software, communication methods, remote collaboration, ethics, and human rights. Based on web traffic monitoring coupled with personal testimonials, we have thousands of users worldwide in academia, industry, open communities and the public sector. The project has inspired and informed research community practices across the STEM sector, including the Office for National Statistics and The Health Foundation.

We delivered eleven workshop presentations in 2021, many of which were led by community members directly to peers in their domains of expertise. In 2022, *The Turing Way* is additionally hosting public, virtual "fireside chats" on topics such as training material translation and alternative academic careers. We are extending our impact, and aligning with our values, by convening experts from across open research communities such as Metadocencia, The Carpentries, Open Life Science, and 2i2c to build solidarity in the actioning of EDI principles across the data science ecosystem.

*3.2) Please outline how your initiative or project has engendered and supported positive change (500 words **maximum**). Please include any supporting evidence to demonstrate impact (for example, relevant statistics, supporting statements from individuals who have benefitted from the project, press coverage etc.)*

Since *The Turing Way's* launch in 2019, over 300 contributors have co-authored more than 200 subchapters describing data science practices on reproducible research, communication to diverse audiences, remote and distributed collaboration, data-intensive project design and research ethics. The online guides are accessed by thousands of users each month and have been replicated, cited and built on widely. Our impact is reflected in nearly 20,000 cumulative downloads of *The Turing Way* resources from Zenodo.

The Turing Way has influenced inclusive practices at national and international research organisations including The Health Foundation, Library Carpentries and the Office for National Statistics. The project is referenced in the international scoping report on Reproducibility of 'Scientific Results by the European Union' and 'An Emerging Technology Charter for London' by the Mayor of London. In 2021, *The Turing Way* was nominated for an OpenUK Award in Sustainability and highly commended by the HiddenRef Award for recognising the importance of hidden labour in academia.

The project has inspired researchers to re-examine their research practices and embed reproducibility and ethical considerations at the centre of what they do. Over time the number of people has grown who advocate for best practices in their communities amplifying a diverse set of voices that represent *The Turing Way*. We provide some highlights and testimonials below:

"Although the international language of science is English, I know for a fact that not everyone in places like Latin-American have the time and resources to learn it, so I think we must do everything we can to break those barriers and improve the accessibility of knowledge for

everyone. This is my motivation to translate the book to Spanish.” – **Camila Rangel-Smith**, Data Scientists at the Turing and Co-lead of LA-CoNGA Physics - Latin-American alliance for Capacity building

“Attending the Turing Way Book Dash event was an eye-opener. The infrastructure and the principles were laid out. It was both impressive and compelling. The meeting allowed two things: Build trust in the technology stack and Access to a Community of Users and Practice.” – Authors of FAIR Cookbook

“We always advocate for software reuse and collaborative development of software. I love that we can do the same for software development guides: reuse content from the eScience guide and collaboratively develop with *The Turing Way* community!” – **Carlos Martinez-Ortiz**, Community Manager, Netherlands eScience Center

“I had never really considered the importance of the reproducibility of my code. Now I can’t imagine ever not doing it. It’s great to be in an environment that is supporting us as we learn these difficult skills that are not yet part of mainstream academic culture.” - **Maxine Mackintosh**, previous PhD student at the Turing, currently [Diverse Data](#) team lead, Genomics England

“Learning more about data science, data management and dissemination and open science has certainly accelerated my thinking and my skills. I’ve gone on to talk about open science and *The Turing Way*, used it in supervising undergraduate students and founding the Athens PyLadies chapter. I’ve truly been inspired.” – **Katerina Drakoulaki**, humanities PhD student

3.3) Please outline any features of your project that are new or innovative in your field of activity. (500 words maximum).

Reproducible research ensures that all results can be easily accessed, independently verified and built upon in future work. This is easier said than done. Sharing data and code requires a common understanding of open technology, data management, software development, collaboration and ethics: skills that are often not widely or practically taught. *The Turing Way* project aims to fill this gap in research and data science by integrating considerations of the societal and ethical implications of our work.

The project is participatory, and has been designed for co-creation from the start.

The Turing Way is a book, a community, an open science project and a global collaboration. We cultivate an inclusive, kind and inspiring community of international researchers and contributors who collaboratively seek to improve how we conduct research for the benefit of science and society. All this work is conducted in open, challenging the disconnected and isolated nature of the traditional academic research process.

Traditionally, open science has been siloed from work to improve research culture, including EDI initiatives and research ethics reform. *The Turing Way* community integrates these efforts to make our project most beneficial and impactful. We deliver this innovation by trusting and empowering individuals and groups with diverse skills, backgrounds, lived experiences and domain knowledge. We are driven by the needs and wishes of our contributors at all times.

We avoid individual authorship in favour of establishing shared ownership and agency in the project. We understand that if we do not recognise all contributions, we will end up disproportionately ignoring the hidden labour that a lot of people undertake, especially those who have historically been excluded from Open Source and STEM spaces across industry, academia and the public sector.

We incorporate universal design principles in all our resources, considering online accessibility, language and disability requirements. Our style guide was developed in 2020 to ensure consistency and high quality communication across all guides. We provide asynchronous support via GitHub, Slack, and online documentation, as well as synchronous support via mentoring for contributors and coworking calls for collaborators.

The Turing Way Book Dash events provide a participatory platform for respectful co-creation and celebration of community-led work. We have experimented with community shared lunches where we share a meal together over Zoom, and “show and tell” social events to learn more about each other’s cultures and personal interests. We ensure contributors can participate by hosting sessions across multiple time zones, providing a budget for the final day’s public celebration event, and offering support grants to cover accessibility related expenses.

At the start of the COVID19 pandemic *The Turing Way* guide supported the transition of hundreds of community members from in-person to virtual working models. We had already been working on the content before the world needed to make these unprecedented changes. The book has dedicated chapters that teach the relevance of EDI principles and the ethical implications of data science in the real world. We are proud that our community promotes these inclusive practices within their research projects and beyond.

3 3.4) Please outline how your initiative or project will be sustained (500 words maximum). Your answer may include details of how the changes engendered by your initiative or project will be/are being embedded and maintained in your organisation or the wider STEM community in the short- and long-term.

The Turing Way is a flagship project at The Alan Turing Institute, The UK’s National Institute for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence. We work across the Skills, Academic Engagement, and Research Engineering teams, and as part of the [Tools, Practices and Systems](#) (TPS) Programme, to ensure that best practices in data science and research are embedded across all projects at the Institute. The TPS Programme represents a cross-cutting set of initiatives which seek to build open source infrastructure that is accessible to all, and to empower a global, decentralised network of people who connect data with domain experts.

In 2021, the Institute made a long-term investment in expanding the TPS Programme to 11 full-time members, including Community Managers, and Research Application Managers. Community Managers build, customise and promote a collaborative framework to ensure that everyone who wants to can participate in research. Research Application Managers bring the perspective of potential users of the research outputs from the early stages of research, supporting the reuse of outputs. As a collective team, TPS members contribute toward building interconnected systems of open-source software, datasets, communities and

processes. They also provide cross-programme training in reproducible research to groups such as early career researchers.

TPS Community Managers and Research Application Managers are core members of [The Turing Way](#) team. They are responsible for the active adoption of open, reproducible, collaborative and inclusive approaches in the projects they are assigned to at the Institute. They also mentor and support researchers to contribute back to *The Turing Way* in a bi-directional model of peer knowledge exchange. Long term plans include extending this model beyond the Turing, to upskill and empower data science researchers across global institutions to act as best practice reproducibility and reuse champions and via collaboration with international organisations.

The Turing Way is designed as a socio-technical infrastructure for community-based development, maintenance and long-term sustainability. All the project outputs belong to *The Turing Way* community, and everyone can freely read, reuse, distribute, modify, and contribute back to the resources in the book. We foster a culture of collaboration by creating equitable opportunities for community participation and enabling an inclusive workspace by providing a clear code of practice and contributing guidelines. To ensure that community members can take part irrespective of their previous experience, we provide the resources, guidance, templates and training to help them stay involved in the community. Current members provide mentorship for new members and drive the adoption of practices in their organisation. The community handbook provides documentation and technical details about the project allowing anyone to reuse its resources to build similar projects from scratch. The shared responsibilities of the project at the Turing as well as the international volunteer community has allowed *The Turing Way* to ensure sustainability of its resources in the long term. An additional community manager will support the project co-leads and focus on the co-development of a governance model for *The Turing Way* to transition the project to the next level of maturity.

3.5) Please outline any plans to replicate or extend your initiative or project, or evidence of successful replication or extension (500 words maximum). Your answer may include details and evidence of how your project or initiative has been shared, adopted or adapted by others in your organisation or the wider STEM community, or details of any plans to do this in the future.

The Turing Way is not only directed towards researchers at The Alan Turing Institute but is more broadly used by people working in data science as part of national and international research communities. Hence, it is important to consider what practices from our projects are transferable and should be shared in *The Turing Way* to benefit other researchers. TPS members collaborate closely with researchers and identify where they can surface implicit knowledge and make information explicitly available via The Turing Way, to transfer practices across the globe and benefit other researchers. Their work at the system level ensures that the research that happens at the Institute is created so it can be maintained, sustained, remixed and adopted in the real world.

The Turing Way community members regularly promote the benefits of reproducible, collaborative and inclusive research at conferences, external communities, workshops and policy advocacy work. Last year, The Turing Way was featured in keynote talks at Open

Science FAIR, Jornadas Argentina de Informática Virtuales – 50 JAIO and Society of Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology and Evolutionary Biology.

In total, The Turing Way members delivered 39 international conference talks and 11 training workshops in 2021. Both long-term contributors and project co-leads take active roles in representing the project. One of the most important community-led extensions within The Turing Way is the translation of its resources into multiple languages, expanding the reach of data science practices more globally. Currently, the project is being translated into Spanish, French, Chinese and Arabic. These members involved in the initiative have also collaborated to create an accessible platform for other researchers to contribute and replicate their work in other languages.

As well as developing its thriving and diverse community, The Turing Way has engaged in collaborations and advocacy work to encourage reproducible research and collaborative and inclusive research cultures. As a result of these engagements, we have influenced multiple research communities and Data Science projects, and have been cited by more than 20 peer-reviewed articles and nearly 100 online publications. We have inspired the following knowledge sharing projects that replicate The Turing Way's practices and formats for online repository and community-led initiatives:

- [Quality Assurance of Code for Analysis and Research](#), Office for National Statistics
- [Turing Data Stories](#), Turing Research Software Engineering team
- [FAIR Cookbook](#) by researchers at University of Oxford, University of Oxford, Novartis and FAIRplus Consortium Members
- [The Environmental Data Science book](#) AI for Science and Government Research Programme
- [The Good Research Code Handbook](#), Patrick J Mineault
- [UCL Institute of Health Informatics Coding Club Handbook](#), University College London
- [A Citizen Science Guide for Research Libraries](#), LIBER Citizen Science Working Group

The Turing Way has collaborated with [Binder](#) to host Turing Federation BinderHub, to support their service of providing a research platform for executable code and data analysis. The 2i2c (<https://2i2c.org/>) organisation has received an Essential Open Source Software for Science grant to collaborate with The Turing Way and build a community strategy to onboard and mentor members from historically underrepresented groups in the JupyterHub community.

Relevant Links:

- Online Book (website): <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome>
- Project repository: <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way>
- Twitter handle: <https://twitter.com/turingway>
- Quarterly reports: https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way/tree/tps-report-2020/project_management/quarterly_reports

- Impact story:
<https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/impact-stories/changing-culture-data-science>
- Other resources on Zenodo under CC-BY license:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/the-turing-way>
- YouTube channels with project resources and updates:
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPDxZv5BMzAw0mPobCbMNUA>

Section 5 – Nominated Referee 1 This section is for the nominator to complete

Dr. Rachael Ainsworth, Community Manager, [Software Sustainability Institute, UK](#)

Section 6 – Nominated Referee 2 This section is for the nominator to complete

Dr. Chris Holdgraf, Director of 2i2c: The International Interactive Computing Collaboration,
Project lead for JupyterHub distributions